

TRANSITION METAL COMPLEX CATALYSED MANNICH REACTION OF PHENOL

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ABSTRACT

The mannich reaction is the most of the important carbon – carbon bond forming reactions in organic reactions . They involve the condensation of the aldehyde or ketones an amine. they forms as a beta amino carbonyl compound. Which is the important intermediate in pharmaceutical , or natural products, polymer chemistry.

When combine with transition metal such as Ni(II) , Cu(II), Co(II) these mannich bases ligand shows the stable coordination complex with enhanced structural, catalytic and biological properties. This all-review focus on the synthesis , structural, catalytic behaviour of the transition metal complexes they derived of the phenolic mannich bases. So, they contain the high purity solids with the good thermal stability.

Keywords:- In mannich reaction carbon carbon bond formation product form beta amino ketone . Catalyst used :- Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺. It enhanced catalytic properties.

INTRODUCTION

The mannich reaction is the fundamental reactions in organic chemistry. The mannich reaction is a forming of carbon C-C bond reaction includes the amine, formaldehyde or another aldehyde and an active hydrogen compound. They provide the beta amino carbonyl compounds, Schiff base,

and amino derivative, which intermediate in pharmaceuticals, coordination chemistry and organic synthesis.

The mannich reaction is evolved acid-catalysed processes, like the solvent free

system, also catalysed free system and as well as graphene oxide-catalysed.

These experiments doing because they enhance yield, selectivity , and environmental sustainability while minimizing reaction time.

They use of graphene oxide as a carbonaceous acid catalyst has efficient approach for mannich reaction. GO possesses abundant oxygen containing functional groups that act as mild sites, enabling the synthesis of beta amino ketones with high yield under the solvent free conditions.

In recent year, the transition metals such as Ni, Cu, Zn, Co etc . into mannich bases has attracted to attention due to their ability to form stable coordination complexes and their enhanced chemical, biological and catalytic properties. The electron bonding oxygen and nitrogen atoms present in mannich bases. They act as the allowing strong coordination with transition metal ions.

This type of metal – mannich complexes exhibit a wide range of application in catalysis, particularly in the hydroxylation of aromatic compounds such as phenol and benzene, as well as in biological and electrochemical systems.

The use of transition metal catalysis improves the selectivity , efficiency and yield of this reaction under the mild and environmental condition.

The solvent free methods used in modern mannich reactions reduce the environmental impact , making this method a sustainable alternative in chemical synthesis. The structural flexibility and multifunctional nature complexes make the applications in organic synthesis, Material science, and medical chemistry. Therefore , the study of transition metal of mannich reaction provides an important way to developing new bioactive compounds and catalysts, importance in both academic research and industrial applications

MECHANISM

Mannich reaction is multistep process that involves the formation of a carbon- carbon bond between amine- formaldehyde and compound containing active hydrogen atom.

- The amine reacts with the formaldehyde or other aldehyde to form an iminium ion intermediate.

• Step :-1.

- The active hydrogen compound such as phenol they form an enol intermediate, which attacks the iminium ion.
- Rearrangement indicates to the beta amino carbonyl compound and corresponds to the mannich base.

- **Formation of metal- Ligands complex** :- The phenolic mannich base ligand coordinate to the metal ion through the nitrogen and oxygen atoms forming a stable chelate complex. Enhance the electron density on the metal centre.
- substrate (phenol) :- the transition metal activates the aromatic substrate by formation of an intermediate metal oxa or metal peroxy species in the presence of oxidants.

METHOD / PROCEDURE :-

The mannich reaction is commonly

The procedure is , of the three reactants – an amine, formaldehyde solution and an active hydrogen compound such as, para-ortho substituted phenol, substituted reactant or main catalyst and ethanol or other solvent such as acetonitrile etc. is added in it then they all are mixed in round bottom flask. The reaction mixture was stirred at 1 or ½ hours if reaction is not complete in R.M. then heated at a temperature of 60-100⁰ C for 2-3 hours under solvent- free conditions. transition Metal complex, which is filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried.

After complete the reaction the mixture was cooled at R.M. the solid forms filtered and

• Step:2

• Step:~3

performed the condensation of an amine, formaldehyde and a compound containing an active hydrogen atom such as a phenol, catechol, and ketone. This process can carry out under solvent- free, metal free conditions depending on the desired product type- simple mannich base , metal complex, or heterocyclic compound.

washed with ethanol or water. If the reaction mixture is liquid, then they extracted from the ethyl acetate and washed with water and dry with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Solvent evaporated under reduced pressure the solid product is formed. Then do the column chromatography. Yield obtains about 70-85%.

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF REACTION TABLE:-

catalyst	Reaction type	Condition	Mechanis-m	Time	Yield
solvent free	Mannich reaction	Solvent free mild chelating	Imine formation – electrophilic addition on phenol ring .	30- 90 minutes(due to solvent free heating).	70- 90%
transition metal(Ni, Cu,Zn)	Mannich base comple- xation	Reflux in ethanol	Mannich base ligand – metal coordination vis N,O donor atoms.	2-4 hrs.	60- 85%
Graphene Oxide	Heterogene -ous	Room temperature at 60 ⁰ C with GO	GO activates carbonyl + formaldehyde – iminium ion- beta addition.	1-1/2 hrs.	80- 95%
Coordinat ion Polymer	Cyclization via mannich type intermediat -e.	Metal free , mild acid is used at 40- 60 ⁰ C.	Mannich intermediate- intramolecular cyclization – dihydrobenzo furan.	6- 24 hrs	60- 80%
Metal free organocat alysts /acid catalysts .	Catalytic hydroxylati on.	Solution synthesis, and hydrotherm al	Coordination framework formation via ligand – metal binding .	1-3 hrs	65- 90%
Metal salt forming complexe s (Ni,Cu,Zn)	Chelating metal complexes.	Reflux with ligand and metal salt.	Chelating stable metal complexes	2-5 hrs	90%

CHARACTERISATION :-

The characterisation of the products synthesis of the mannich reaction and its variations was performed using a combination of spectroscopic, analytical, and electrochemical techniques to confirm

structure, purity, and bonding nature of the mannich bases, metal complexes they obtained from each method. The characterisation is done by some instrumental techniques such as UV visible

spectroscopy , IR spectroscopy , ¹H NMR etc.

APPLICATIONS AND ADVANTAGES :-

Applications

- In drug synthesis they used to prepare the anticancer, antiviral, antibacterial drugs.
- The formation of the beta amino compounds they show the important role to building blocks in medicines and organic synthesis.
- The metal mannich reaction complexes used in electrochemical and optical sensors.
- In industrial uses they used the corrosion inhibitors, lubricants, surfactants, and resin .

Advantages :-

1. Efficiency is high product yield (70-90%) under the solvent- free or ecofriendly condition.
2. Selectivity of metal coordination directs the reaction pathway , improving regio- and stereochemistry.
3. Stability shows the high thermal and oxidative stability . Complexes are often crystalline, easy to isolate and store.
4. Multifunctionality combines the catalytic, magnetic, optical, and electrochemical feature in one compound.
5. Metal complexes show enhanced antibacterial, anticancer, antifungal, antioxidant activity .

Outcome

1. The reaction produces stable transition metal- mannich base complexes with high yield (70-95%) .
2. Formed complexes shows defined geometries like octahedral or square planer depending on the metal .(Cu ,Ni, Co, Zn)
3. The products exhibit enhanced biological activity- antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant , anticancer properties which is their superior to the parent mannich bases due to enhanced metal – ligand interaction.
4. They act as effective in organic and electrochemical reactions.
5. The process follows green chemistry principle, often the solvent free and energy efficient.

CONCLUSION

1. The transition metal mannich reaction is an efficient and ecofriendly method for synthesizing stable and biologically active metal complexes.
2. It offers high yields, selectivity , and mild reaction conditions following green chemistry principles.
3. The resulting complexes show enhanced thermal stability , catalytic efficiency and strong biological activity such as antibacterial , antifungal, anticancer etc.

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